

Tin(IV) Selenophosphate for Separation and Determination of Chromium, Nickel and Iron in Super Alloys

SYED ASHFAQ NABI^a and ZIA MAHMOOD SIDDIQI^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

^bDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Dr. B. R. A. Regional Engineering College, Jalandhar-144 027

Manuscript received 8 October 1991, revised 10 May 1993, accepted 19 August 1993

The practical utility of the separations of metal ions on synthetic inorganic ion-exchangers have not been much explored. Recently, rock sample and alloy constituents have been separated on zirconium arsenophosphate¹. Semicrystalline tin(IV) selenophosphate has been synthesised and studied by us for its properties with few simple binary, ternary and quaternary separations of metal ion^{2,3}. The present work illustrates the wider utility of this ion-exchanger. High temperature super alloys are selected for study as no attempt has been made to separate the metal ions in such samples utilising an inorganic ion-exchanger.

Results and Discussion

The main constituents of the alloys are Cr, Ni and Fe as we find out from standard chemical composition of these alloys. The INCONEL-600 has Ni and the INCONEL-800 has Fe as the main constituents. The amounts of other species in the alloy solutions which are applied on the columns of tin(IV) selenophosphate are negligible. Sulphur, carbon and silicon are passed through the column unadsorbed along with Cr^{VI}. The quaternary separations, Cr^{VI}-Ni^{II}-Cu^{II}-Fe^{III} and Cr^{VI}-Ni^{II}-Mn^{II}-Fe^{III} have been achieved on the small columns of tin(IV) selenophosphate on the basis of differential uptake of these metal ions by the ion-exchange material in various media³. Cr^{VI} came out with distilled water in the effluent, whereas Ni^{II} and Fe^{III} were eluted by 4 M DMF + 0.5 M HNO₃ (2 : 8) and 1 M HNO₃ respectively. Small quantities of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} were removed from the column by 0.1 M HNO₃ to prevent

their interference in the determination of Ni^{II} and Fe^{III}.

Table 1 shows a variation in results for samples 1 and 2 which is due to same amount of exchanger (0.5 g) in the column and hence the possibility of errors may be minimised either by taking small volumes of metal ion solutions or larger quantity of exchanger for separation. Crystallinity of the ion-exchanger showed the reversible properties. The results of Table 2 indicate the same behaviour of semicrystalline tin(IV) selenophosphate.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF CHROMIUM, NICKEL AND IRON IN THE SAMPLES OF SUPER ALLOY ON TIN(IV) SELENOPOSPHATE

Sample no.	Separation achieved	Eluent used	Total elution ml	Amount taken µg	Amount found µg	% Error
INCONEL-600 :						
1.	Cr ^{VI}	H ₂ O	10	40	40	0.0
	Ni ^{II}	DMF + HNO ₃	40	199.9	195.9	2.0
	Fe ^{III}	HNO ₃	30	105	102.0	2.0
2.	Cr ^{II}	H ₂ O	10	60	57	5.0
	Ni ^{II}	DMF + HNO ₃	30	299.9	284	5.2
	Fe ^{III}	HNO ₃	50	157.5	174.6	10.8
INCONEL-800 :						
1.	Cr ^{VI}	H ₂ O	30	72	72	0.0
	Ni ^{II}	DMF + HNO ₃	40	110	108	1.4
	Fe ^{III}	HNO ₃	30	156	152	2.5
2.	Cr ^{VI}	H ₂ O	40	108	106.4	1.5
	Ni ^{II}	DMF + HNO ₃	40	165	155	6.1
	Fe ^{III}	HNO ₃	30	234	224	5.1

TABLE 2—REPRODUCIBILITY IN THE DETERMINATION OF Cr^{VI}, Ni^{II} AND Fe^{III} IN INCONEL-600 AND INCONEL-800

Sl. no.	Amount loaded (µg)			Amount found (µg)			%Error			Standard deviation
	Cr ^{VI}	Ni ^{II}	Fe ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}	Ni ^{II}	Fe ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}	Ni ^{II}	Fe ^{III}	
INCONEL-600 :										
1.	60	299.9	157.5	57	284	174.6	5.0	5.2	10.8	Cr ^{VI} = 0.660
2.	60	299.9	157.5	57	285	173.0	5.0	4.9	9.8	
3.	60	299.9	157.5	56	284	174.0	6.6	5.2	10.5	
4.	60	299.9	157.5	56	284	174.9	6.6	5.2	11.4	Ni ^{II} = 0.857
5.	60	299.9	157.5	57	286	175.0	5.0	4.6	11.1	
6.	60	299.9	157.5	58	283	174.6	3.3	5.6	10.8	Fe ^{III} = 0.382
7.	60	299.9	157.5	57	284	174.5	5.0	5.2	10.7	
8.	60	299.9	157.5	56	285	174.0	6.6	4.9	10.5	
INCONEL-800 :										
1.	108	165	234	106.4	155	224	1.5	6.1	5.1	Cr ^{VI} = 0.449
2.	108	165	234	106.0	152	223	1.9	7.9	4.7	
3.	108	165	234	107.0	154	225	0.93	6.7	3.9	
4.	108	165	234	106.0	154	224	1.9	5.7	5.1	Ni ^{II} = 0.735
5.	108	165	234	106.0	154	223	1.9	6.7	4.7	
6.	108	165	234	106.0	152	223	1.9	7.9	4.7	Fe ^{III} = 0.466
7.	108	165	234	107.0	152	224	0.93	7.9	5.1	
8.	108	165	234	107.0	155	225	0.93	6.1	3.9	

Experimental

Tin(IV) chloride (Baker Analyzed, U.S.A.), sodium selenite (B.D.H.) and sodium dihydrogen phosphate (B.D.H.) were used for the synthesis of tin(IV) selenophosphate. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade.

The spectrophotometry was performed on an EC GS 865D spectrophotometer.

Semicrystalline tin(IV) selenophosphate was synthesised by mixing 0.05 M solutions of tin(IV) chloride, sodium selenite and potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1 : 1 : 2 volume ratio at pH 0. The precipitate was kept overnight, then filtered, dried at 40° and converted to H⁺-form as described earlier². This ion-exchanger (50–100 mesh) was used for column purpose.

Preparation of solutions of alloys : INCONEL-600 alloy (0.6575 g) was heated with a mixture (80 ml) of 16 M phosphoric acid and 12 M perchloric acid (1 : 1, v/v). It was boiled to evaporate the excess acid. Solution of INCONEL-800 (0.8660 g)

was prepared in the same manner in a mixture of phosphoric acid and perchloric acid (1 : 1; 100 ml). Both the solutions were diluted upto 500 ml with distilled water. 10 ml of these solutions were further diluted and made upto 100 ml with distilled water.

The analyses of the alloys were as follows : INCONEL-600, Mn, 0.2; Fe, 6.66; Cu, 0.16; Ni, 76.95; Cr, 15.58; C, 0.06; S, 0.007; Si, 0.38; and INCONEL-800, Mn, 0.815; Fe, 45.14; Cu, 0.29; Ni, 31.98; Cr, 20.99; C, 0.09; S, 0.007; Si, 0.67.

Procedure for separations : The ion-exchange column was prepared using an earlier method⁴. A glass column (i.d. 0.6 cm) was used with 2 g of ion-exchange material (50–100 mesh) in H⁺-form. Different volumes of the solutions of alloys were applied on the exchanger bed. The metal ions were allowed to be adsorbed by passing the solution of alloys several times through the column at 25 ± 2°. Chromium alongwith S, Si and carbon were not exchanged and came out

NOTE

along the washing with distilled water. Nickel and iron were then eluted by suitable eluting reagents. The flow rate of effluent was maintained at 1 ml min⁻¹. The metal ions were collected in 10 ml fraction and determined by standard methods^{4,5}. Table 1 shows the results.

The reproducibility of the method was checked by carrying out the separations several times (Table 2).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. K. G. VARSHNEY, S. AGRAWAL, K. VARSHNEY, A. PREMADAS, M. S. RATHI and P. P. KHANNA, *Talanta*, 1983, **30**, 687.
2. S. A. NABI and Z. M. SIDDIQI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1986, **59**, 1281.
3. S. A. NABI and Z. M. SIDDIQI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1985, **58**, 2380.
4. S. A. NABI, Z. M. SIDDIQI and W. U. FAROOQI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, **55**, 2442.
5. N. H. FURMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 6th ed., Van Nostrand, Princeton, 1962, Vol. 1, p. 359.
6. S. A. NABI and Z. M. SIDDIQI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1985, **58**, 724.

